

Assessing the Impact of His-Tags on Activity and Stability of Staphylokinase Variants

Monika Štulajterová^{1¶}, Ľuboš Ambro^{2¶}, Dagmar Sedláková^{3¶}, Michal Nemergut², Pavel Kohout⁴, Stanislav Mazurenko⁴, Rastislav Varhač⁵, Alan Strunga⁴, Martin Toul⁴, Zbyněk Prokop⁴, Jiří Damborský^{4*}, Mária Tomková^{2*}, Erik Sedlák^{2,5*}

¹Department of Biophysics, Faculty of Science, P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Jesenná 5, 04154 Košice, Slovakia

²Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Jesenná 5, 04154 Košice, Slovakia

³Department of Biophysics, Institute of Experimental Physics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Watsonova 47, 040 01 Košice, Slovakia

⁴Loschmidt Laboratories, Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5/C13, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic; International Clinical Research Center, St. Anne's University Hospital, Pekarska 53, 656 91 Brno, Czech Republic

⁵Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Science, P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Moyzesova 11, 04154 Košice, Slovakia

¶ The authors contributed equally to this work

* To whom correspondence should be addressed:

Centre for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Jesenná 5, 04154 Košice, Slovakia; email: erik.sedlak@upjs.sk

Centre for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Jesenná 5, 04154 Košice, Slovakia; email: maria.tomkova@upjs.sk

Loschmidt Laboratories, Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5/C13, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic; International Clinical Research Center, St. Anne's University Hospital, Pekarska 53, 656 91 Brno, Czech Republic; email: 1441@mail.muni.cz

Abstract

Staphylokinase (SAK), a potent plasminogen activator, is a promising thrombolytic agent, but its clinical application is limited by immunogenicity and stability concerns. In addition to intrinsic sequence variants, recombinant protein production often introduces affinity tags, such as the N-terminal polyhistidine (His-tag), whose potential effects on protein's biophysical and functional properties remain poorly understood. Here, we systematically investigated the impact of His-tagging on the stability and activity of four SAK variants: wild-type and non-immunogenic (triple-alanine, 3A) forms of two naturally occurring SAK types, SAK STAR and SAK 42D. Thermal and pH stability were assessed using circular dichroism and tryptophan fluorescence spectroscopy, and plasminogen-activating efficiency was evaluated through chromogenic assays. We found that while the His-tag had little effect on thermal stability and only modestly influenced functional activity, it significantly destabilized SAK under acidic conditions, and altered unfolding transitions, indicating the presence of intermediate conformations. Among the tested proteins, SAK STAR demonstrated the best structural and functional robustness, whereas SAK 42D 3A was the least stable and most prone to aggregation. These results highlight the need to assess the biophysical effect of affinity tags and point SAK STAR as the most suitable candidate for next therapeutic development.

1. Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases, such as ischemic stroke and myocardial infarction, are among the leading causes of death and disability worldwide [1]. The recent global COVID-19 pandemic has contributed to the high incidence of cardiovascular diseases, as patients who have recovered from COVID-19 have an elevated risk of ischemic cardiovascular complications for up to one year post-infection [2]. Although pharmacological thrombolysis and mechanical thrombectomy have improved patient outcomes, currently approved thrombolytics - recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rt-PA) and its variants - suffer from narrow therapeutic windows, suboptimal efficacy, and bleeding risks [3–8]. This underscores the urgent need for safer and more effective thrombolytic agents.

Staphylokinase (SAK), a small protein secreted by *Staphylococcus aureus*, has emerged as a highly fibrin-specific plasminogen activator with favourable therapeutic potential [9–11]. SAK is a 15.5 kDa without any disulfide bridges or posttranslational modifications [12]. SAK offers an advantage over other thrombolytic agents due to its high fibrin selectivity, meaning it converts plasminogen only near the thrombus and does not induce systemic plasminogen activation [13], thereby reducing bleeding complications. There are three well characterized natural variants of SAK, which differ in three amino acid positions 34, 36, and 43: SAK42D – Gly34, Arg36, Arg43, SAK STAR – Ser34, Gly36, His43 and SAKΦC – Gly34, Gly36, His43. These minor amino acid substitutions do not alter the protein conformational properties at physiological temperatures but affect the protein kinetic stabilities [14].

Over the years, one of the major obstacles to the widespread clinical use of SAK was its immunogenicity. SAK, upon its repeated administration leads to its neutralization and may potentially trigger an inflammatory reaction [15]. Therefore, significant effort was devoted to developing variants of SAK with reduced immunoreactivity. This goal was achieved by substituting three surface-exposed charged amino acids, Lys74, Glu75, and Arg77, with alanines, resulting in a 200-fold reduction in antibody formation [16]. This non-immunogenic variant of SAK, here denoted as 3A variant has already been used in the treatment of ischemic stroke [9,10]; however, despite its clinical utility in Russia, it has not yet attained FDA approval.

Figure 1. Comparison of the primary (A) and tertiary (B) structures of SAK variants (PDB ID: 2SAK). Residues highlighted in green represent stabilization mutations distinguishing STAR from 42D. Residues highlighted in yellow correspond to substitutions in non-immunogenic variants (3A). The blue-highlighted sequence indicates a 13-amino acid fragment removed after purification, with the red mark indicating the TEV protease cleavage site. Dots in the sequences indicate positions identical to those in 42D.

In general, the major limitation of an application of (therapeutic) proteins is their stability, which may be affected by many factors such as temperature, pH or concentration [17]. Another important factor for protein stability, which is in general assumed as non-perturbative, is an affinity tag, such as the polyhistidine tag (His-tag). Although affinity tags can greatly improve and simplify the purification of recombinant proteins [18–20], it has been shown that, in some cases, a His-tag can affect protein structure [21–23], binding interactions with ligands and protein partners [24–30], as well as protein dynamics or stability [31,32]. Very recently, a software package named Terminator was developed to optimize His-tag placement for affinity purification [33]. While the software predicts the relative risk of adverse effects between N- and C-terminal tagging, the actual impact of His-tag localization on protein or enzyme properties must still be determined experimentally. Indeed, recent studies have demonstrated that both the presence and specific placement of a His-tag can alter enzyme activity by inducing structural changes, thereby influencing kinetic and/or colloidal stability [34–37] and even modifying the reaction type, as originally observed in lipases [38]. In this study, we compared conformational stabilities of eight SAK variants in dependence on temperature and pH, as well as their enzymatic activity at physiological conditions. These variants include immunogenic (native) and non-immunogenic (3A) forms of two naturally occurring variants SAK STAR and SAK 42D, each with and without a His-tag (Figure 1, Table S1). Only the effects of N-terminal

His-tags on SAK variants have been tested, as the C-terminal residues are critically important for SAK activity [39]. This study aimed to characterize the properties of the individual SAK forms, with and without a His-tag, to assess their potential for further enhancement of conformational and functional features through rational design and directed protein evolution, while also highlighting possible drawbacks of His-tagging that arise from the specific structural context of the protein.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Plasmid Information. The genes encoding SAK variants were cloned into the plasmid pET-21b (+) (T7, Amp resistance), designed to produce proteins with an N-terminal 6His-tag followed by a TEV-cleavage site. TEV protease was cloned into the pMAL plasmid (T7, Amp resistance) and designed as N-terminal fusion with maltose binding protein C-terminal 7His-tag.

2.2. Transformation and Culture. Plasmids were transformed into chemically competent *E. coli*: BL21 (DE3) for SAK and chloramphenicol-resistant BL21 (DE3) RIPL for TEV protease, via heat shock method (45s at 42°C). Cells were recovered in 2xYT medium (30 min at 37°C) and then plated on 2xYT agar plates supplemented with corresponding antibiotics (100 µg/ml ampicillin and 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol). Transformants were used to generate overnight cultures (18h at 37°C) that served as inoculum for expression cultures (diluted to OD₆₀₀ = 0.1). Cultures were grown at 37°C until OD₆₀₀ reached 0.6–0.8. Protein expression was induced with IPTG (0.1 mM for SAK and 0.5 mM for TEV), proteins were produced for 18 hours at 20°C. Bacterial cultures were centrifuged, and pellets were frozen with liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C.

2.3. SAK Purification. For SAK purification, cell pellets were resuspended in a buffer containing 50 mM Hepes, 200 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 7mM lysozyme, and protease inhibitors (10 µM leupeptin and 1 µM pepstatin). The cells were lysed by sonication (Branson Sonifier 450, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Lysates were centrifuged 30 min at 17 500g at 4°C, and supernatants were subjected to affinity chromatography. Gravity column filled with Ni-NTA matrix (ThermoFisher Scientific) equilibrated with 50 mM Hepes, 200 mM NaCl. After loading the supernatant, column was washed with 50 mM Hepes, 200 mM NaCl, 40 mM imidazole to remove contaminants. Subsequently, proteins were eluted with buffer containing 50 mM Hepes, 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, and 10% glycerol.

Eluted proteins were concentrated using Amicon ® Ultra Centrifugal Filter, 10 kDa MWCO (Merck, Germany) and further purified using a Superdex 75 Increase 10/300 GL size-

exclusion chromatography column equilibrated with 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.5). Protein purity was assessed by 15% SDS-PAGE, and gels were stained with InstantBlue Coomassie stain (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Fractions exhibiting the highest purity were pooled, flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at -80°C .

2.4. TEV Protease Purification. The purification of TEV protease followed a similar protocol with minor adjustments. Bacterial pellets were lysed with a buffer containing 16.5 mM K_2HPO_4 , 3.5 mM KH_2PO_4 , 500 mM NaCl, and 5 mM imidazole and supernatant subjected to affinity chromatography. After loading the supernatant, the column was washed with the same buffer that was used for cell lysis. TEV was eluted with buffer containing 16.5 mM K_2HPO_4 , 3.5 mM KH_2PO_4 , 500 mM NaCl, and 500 mM imidazole. Eluted protein was dialyzed overnight at 8°C in 50 mM phosphate buffer, purified on a Superdex 75 Increase 10/300 GL size-exclusion chromatography column, and purity verified by 10% SDS-PAGE.

2.5. Cleavage and Final Purification. Cleavage of His-tag from each SAK variant was achieved by supplementing 5mg purified SAK with TEV protease in a protein to protease ratio 100:1. Mixture was incubated at 4°C overnight. The cleavage by TEV protease resulted in the removal of N-terminal sequence consisting of 13 amino acid residues, MHHHHHHENLYFQ (MW 1767 Da). Upon cleavage, SAK was purified by reverse-IMAC chromatography, where the column was equilibrated with 50 mM phosphate buffer, and the SAK-cleaved protein was collected in flow-through. Protein concentration and purity was confirmed by 15% SDS-PAGE.

2.6. Circular Dichroism Spectra (CD). CD spectra were obtained by measurements on a Jasco J-810 spectropolarimeter with 15 μM SAK variants at 23°C in 10 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.5). Each spectrum is an average of 5 scans. All spectra were background-corrected and converted to mean residue ellipticity and molar ellipticity in the far-UV (190-250 nm) and the aromatic (250-320 nm) spectral regions, respectively. For the peptide and the aromatic regions 1 mm and 1 cm cuvettes were used, respectively.

The quantitative parameters of pH transitions monitored by ellipticity such as the pK_a value and the number of protons, n , associated with the transition were obtained by fitting the experimental data according to Equation (1) in accordance with our previous work [40]:

$$S = \frac{S_N + S_D \cdot 10^{n(\text{pK}_a - \text{pH})}}{1 + 10^{n(\text{pK}_a - \text{pH})}} \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

where S is the experimentally obtained value, i.e. the ellipticity at 215 nm, S_N is value of the parameter for the native state and S_D for the denatured state, pK_a is the pH for the inflection point of the transition, and n is the number of protons associated with the transition.

Protein thermal denaturation was assessed by monitoring the ellipticity at 215 nm as a function of temperature in the range of 20–80°C. Measurements were conducted at a scan rate of 1.5°C/min.

Parameters characterizing the temperature dependence of protein stability, as monitored by ellipticity, were determined by fitting the normalized experimental data to the following equation, as described in our previous work [41]:

$$S = \frac{S_N + S_D \exp \left[\frac{\Delta H_{vH}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_m} \right) \right]}{1 + \exp \left[\frac{\Delta H_{vH}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_m} \right) \right]} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

where S is the measured signal, i.e. the ellipticity at 215 nm, S_N is the signal value for the native state, S_D for the denatured state, ΔH_{vH} is value of van't Hoff enthalpy and T_m is the transition temperature that corresponds to the inflection point of the measured dependence.

2.7. Fluorescence. Fluorescence emission spectra of the studied proteins were recorded by RF-5301PC spectrofluorometer (Shimadzu). The emission spectra of tryptophan were measured by using excitation wavelengths at 295 nm. In all cases, fluorescence spectra were obtained by using 10 μ M protein concentration.

Temperature-induced conformational changes were measured using a Jasco FP-8300 spectrofluorometer. The temperature was controlled using a Jasco ETC-815 accessory. The concentration of all protein variants was 10 μ M. Measurements were performed in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.5. Quartz cuvette with a light path of 10 x 2 mm was used. Temperature interval was set from 20 to 85 °C with scan rate of 1.5 °C/min. Excitation wavelength, excitation and emission slits were set to 290 nm, 5 nm and 2.5 nm, respectively.

Parameters characterizing the temperature dependences of the proteins stability monitored by the ratio of fluorescence emission at 330 and 350 nm. Obtained dependences were obtained from the fit of the normalized experimental data by the Equation (1) and corrected as published previously [42].

The quantitative parameters of pH transitions monitored by fluorescence emission at 350 nm were obtained from the fit of the normalized experimental data by the Equation (1).

2.8. pH Measurements. pH values were determined using a HI 9017 pH meter coupled to a HI 1330 pH electrode (Hanna Instruments). All pH-induced titration measurements were performed at 25 °C, in 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer.

2.9. SAK Activity Measurements. The activity of each SAK variant (His-tagged and native protein) was assessed using an optimized colorimetric assay [13,43], employing the same

concentrations as in the fluorogenic assay [6]. This involved monitoring the change in reaction colour with the chromogenic plasminogen substrate Chromogenix S-2251 (DiaPharma, USA), which reflects plasmin activity generated from plasminogen by plasminogen activators. Plasmin hydrolyses the chromogenic substrate, releasing the chromophoric group pNA, and the reaction colour is read photometrically at 405 nm.

Reaction components were mixed to final concentrations of 6 nM SAK, 6 nM plasmin (Athens Research & Technology, USA), 550 nM plasminogen (Roche Diagnostics, Germany), and 0.7 mM chromogenic substrate. The experiment was conducted at 37°C in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at pH 7.4, containing 1 mM CaCl₂. Each measurement was performed in duplicate in two separate wells of a 96-well clear flat-bottom microplate (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The plate was sealed with a transparent adhesive film to prevent evaporation, and the kinetics of plasminogen activation were monitored by the increase in absorbance at 405 nm using the Synergy BioTek HTX Multimode Reader (Agilent Technologies, USA).

The activity of the SAK variants was analysed in accordance with the method developed by Toul et al. [44]. The shape of the kinetic curve observed during the coupled assay reflects the mechanistic steps of the enzymatic cascade and consists of four distinct phases: the lag phase, the parabolic phase, the linear phase, and the plateau. The most informative and relevant segment for analysing SAK activity is the parabolic phase, during which active plasmin is continuously generated, leading to an acceleration in substrate conversion. In contrast, the linear phase represents the point at which all plasminogen has been converted to plasmin, and substrate hydrolysis proceeds at a constant rate that is independent of SAK activity.

The production of chromogenic product can be described by a quadratic dependence:

$$Signal = a_{app} \cdot t^2$$

(Equation 3)

where a_{app} is an apparent acceleration constant (units: time⁻²) that reflects the time-dependent catalytic enhancement arising from the coupled reaction mechanism, in which the product of the first reaction, plasmin, acts as the enzyme of the second reaction that generates the detectable absorbance signal. It considers the increasing concentration of active plasmin as a result of the action of SAK. This parameter captures the increasing concentration of active plasmin, and consequently the increasing rate of chromogenic substrate conversion, over time due to SAK-mediated activation.

To quantitatively evaluate SAK activity, the kinetic trace was trimmed to include only the parabolic region - defined here by absorbance values between 0.13 and 0.5. This range was selected to exclude both the initial lag and the terminal linear/plateau phases, ensuring that the

fitted region accurately reflects the enzymatic acceleration governed by SAK. The trimmed data were then fitted using the quadratic model represented by the Equation (3).

2.10. BioEmu ensemble generator. For each of the four systems, we generated conformations using BioEmu, a machine-learning-based ensemble generator, employing Model 1.0 from the official GitHub repository (<https://github.com/microsoft/bioemu>). To remove physically implausible structures, we applied the BioEmu filtering script, which filters conformations based on C α -C α and C-N distances between sequential residues and identifies atomic clashes between atoms from different residues. After filtering, 600 conformations per system were retained for further analysis. RMSD, RMSF, and radius of gyration (Rg) metrics were calculated using the MDTraj Python package, with RMSF computed only on C α atoms.

3. Results and Discussion

We produced four SAK variants: two naturally occurring forms, SAK 42D (G34, R36, R43) and SAK STAR (S34, G36, H43), and their non-immunogenic counterparts, each containing three amino acid substitutions (K74A, E75A, and R77A). Differences in their primary and tertiary structures are shown in Figure 1. All proteins contained His-tag for a facilitated purification by affinity chromatography. After expression in *E. coli*, each variant was cleaved with TEV protease, generating the corresponding native proteins, i.e. without His-tag. Throughout this work, we will refer to the His-tagged versions of these proteins as "His-tagged" the cleaved versions as "native" and the non-immunogenic variants as "3A".

3.1. *Circular dichroism and fluorescence of SAK variants.* Circular dichroism in both the far- and near-UV regions as well as the fluorescence spectra of the only Trp66 in the studied SAK variants clearly indicate that neither different mutations in SAK 42D and SAK STAR and their 3A variants, nor the presence of His-tag affect the conformational property of the SAK (Figure 2). The absence of changes in the secondary and tertiary structures of the SAK variants is in agreement with previously reported findings [14].

Figure 2. Circular dichroism and fluorescence spectra of SAK variants. The CD spectra of the proteins are shown in the far-UV region (plots A and D) and the near-UV region (plots B and E). The fluorescence spectra of the proteins are presented in plots C and F. The upper row displays the spectra of His-tagged proteins, while the lower row shows the spectra of native proteins. The SAK variants are represented by the following color scheme: 42D (blue), STAR (red), 42D 3A (green), and STAR 3A (black).

3.2. *Computational analysis.* We have carried out computational analysis of ensembles of two wild-type staphylokinases with and without His-tags. In total, 600 conformations were generated using the computational framework BioEmu [45]. The systems were compared in terms of their Radius of gyration, Pairwise Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) and Root Mean Square Fluctuations (RMSF) per residue (Figure 3). The His-tag variants generally exhibit a slightly broader distribution of the radius of gyration, which is expected given their longer sequence due to the presence of the six additional His residues. However, the overall peak of the distribution remains comparable to that of the non-His-tag variants, suggesting that the tag does not substantially affect protein folding or unfolding. In the all-frame pair RMSD calculations, a very clear shift in the distributions is apparent for the His-tag variants. This effect reflects higher flexibility of the N-terminal part of the protein, which is also indicated by the RMSF plot. The RMSF analysis, with residue alignment and His-tag fluctuations highlighted in bold, indicates that the flexibility distribution is overall similar across the protein, as observed by visual inspection.

3.2. *The pH stabilities of SAK variants.* The presence of His-tag, which contains titratable imidazole groups, suggests a potential effect of pH on the protein's stabilities. The pH stabilities of the SAK variants were assessed by monitoring pH dependences of CD spectra in

Figure 3. Comparison of conformational ensembles of His-tag and non-His-tag variants of staphylokinase. Ensembles of two staphylokinase variants, with and without His-tags, were calculated using BioEmu, resulting in a total of 600 conformations. (A) RMSF per residue, computed on $C\alpha$ atoms, shows that overall flexibility is similar across the protein, with the His-tag region highlighted in bold indicating slightly higher fluctuations at the N-terminal part. (B) Radius of gyration (R_g) demonstrates that His-tag variants generally have a slightly broader distribution due to the six additional His residues, while the overall peak remains comparable to non-His-tag variants, suggesting minimal impact on global folding. (C) Pairwise RMSD distributions reveal a clear shift for His-tag variants, reflecting the higher flexibility of the N-terminal region observed in the RMSF analysis.

the far-UV region and intrinsic Trp66 fluorescence (Figures S1 and S2). The normalized pH dependence of ellipticity at 215 nm and fluorescence amplitudes at 350 nm are shown in Figure 4. Parameters, including the pK_a constant for the pH-induced conformational transition and the number of protons exchanged during the transition, were determined by fitting the data using Equation 1, and are summarized in Table S2. These parameters were determined by analysis of the dependences in the pH range 3-13.

At pH values below 3, one can see an appearance of another transition to a transition reminding molten-globule state at acidic pH [46]. This transition was characterized by an increase in ellipticity in the far-UV region and a rise in fluorescence amplitude, along with a shift in the fluorescence maximum from approximately 350 nm to 340 nm.

In the analysis of pH dependences of SAK variants, we addressed: (i) the presence of intermediate state(s) and (ii) the effect of His-tag on the parameters of the pH transitions. The pK_a values of transitions in the alkaline pH region, monitored by ellipticity at 215 nm, have values in the narrow interval $\sim 11.0 \pm 0.2$ for all His-tagged and native SAK forms. However, these pK_a values were about one pH unit higher than those derived from Trp fluorescence, which were around $\sim 9.9 \pm 0.1$. From these observations, one can conclude: (i) the existence of intermediate(s), (ii) a more pH-resistant secondary structure compared to Trp66 surrounding and likely the α -helix in the SAK structures, and (iii) absence of an effect of His-tag in the pH transitions in the alkaline pH region for all studied SAK variants. These findings can be summarized in the following equation:

where N, I_B and U_B represent native (neutral), intermediate (observed by fluorescence at basic pH) and unfolded (observed by ellipticity at basic pH) forms of SAK variants, respectively. The pK_{F-His} and pK_{F+His} correspond to pK values of the pH transition monitored by tryptophan fluorescence without and with His-tag, respectively. In analogy, pK_{CD-His} and pK_{CD+His} correspond to pK values of the pH transition monitored by ellipticity of SAK variants without and with His-tag, respectively.

In contrast, analogous analyses of the pH transitions in the acidic pH region led to different conclusions for His-tagged SAK variants. The pK_a values of acidic transitions of native variants, obtained from both CD and fluorescence measurements, are similar for each SAK variants indicating all or none pH-induced acidic transition without stable intermediate(s). The observed transition at acidic pH for native SAK variants can be summarized as follows:

where N and U_A represent native (neutral) and pH-unfolded forms of native SAK variants, respectively.

To this end, the pH transitions of His-tagged SAK variants differ from those of native SAK variants. The pK_a values of individual His-tagged SAK variants, monitored by ellipticity at 215 nm and tryptophan fluorescence at 350 nm, significantly differ. For example, the pK_a values monitored by fluorescence and ellipticity differ by ~ 0.3 pH units in SAK 42D (pK_a obtained from CD ~ 6.4 versus pK_a obtained from fluorescence measurements ~ 6.7) up to ~ 0.9 pH unit in SAK 42D 3A (pK_a obtained from CD ~ 5.9 versus pK_a obtained from fluorescence measurements ~ 6.8) (Table S2). Noteworthy, for all His-tagged variants, the pK_a values

obtained from monitoring fluorescence is relatively constant for all SAK variants, $\sim 6.6 \pm 0.2$ and higher than the pK_a values obtained from ellipticity measurements indicating that pH-induced transition at Trp66 does not depend on mutations present in the variants and that the Trp66/ α -helix region precedes the transition/unfolding of the secondary structure represented by β -sheets. This observation is summarized in the following equation:

where I_A designates an intermediate (observed by fluorescence at acidic pH) forms of SAK variants with His-tag.

Comparison of pH stability of His-tagged SAK variants based on acidic pK_a s is meaningless because the presence of His-tag significantly affects the values of pK_a of these transitions in such way that they are all distributed in narrow pH interval from 5.9 to 6.4 monitored by ellipticity and from 6.5 to 6.8 monitored by fluorescence. Similarly, the pK_a values of native SAK obtained by circular dichroism are distributed within the range 5.4 to 6.0. On the other hand, Trp66 represents a sensitive probe of structures of native SAK variants and pH-stability of the SAKs obtained from fluorescence in the acidic pH region can be ordered as follows: **42D > STAR > STAR 3A > 42D 3A**.

Another important conclusion can be drawn from comparison of the pK_a values of the corresponding His-tagged and native SAK variants. In all cases, except for SAK STAR 3A, one can notice a shift in the pK_a transitions to more neutral pH of His-tagged variants monitored by ellipticity for SAK 42D 3A, SAK STAR, and SAK 42D by 0.2, 0.2, and 1.0 pH units, respectively. This observation indicates a destabilization of the His-tag on the secondary structure in the presence at acidic pH. Analogous but significantly more pronounced differences are observed in the pK_a values of acidic transitions of His-tagged and native variants obtained from fluorescence. The presence of His-tag results in destabilization of the tertiary structure by ~ 0.6 , ~ 0.6 , ~ 1.2 , and ~ 1.5 pH units in SAK STAR 3A, SAK 42D 3A, and SAK STAR and SAK 42D, respectively.

Interestingly, the number of protons involved in the acidic pH transitions, which is in all cases ~ 1 , is puzzling and suggests a decoupling of the His protonation from the pH-induced conformational transition. Although the effect of His-tag on acidic pH transition of proteins is

not unexpected, based on our best knowledge, this is the first experimental study reporting this effect.

3.3. Thermal stabilities of the SAK variants. Thermal stabilities of each SAK variant

Figure 4. *pH transitions of the SAK variants.* The pH transitions of His-tagged and native forms of SAK variants are shown in the top and middle rows, respectively: 42D (blue) (A, E), STAR (red) (B, F), 42D 3A (green) (C, G), and STAR 3A (black) (D, H). His-tagged forms are represented by solid symbols, native forms are shown as empty symbols. Histograms enable to compare transition temperatures of the SAK variants obtained by CD and fluorescence of His-tagged forms of SAK (solid histograms) and native SAK forms (empty or hatched histograms).

were assessed using measurements of temperature dependences of: (i) ellipticity at 215 nm, monitoring the secondary structure unfolding (Figure 5A) and (ii) fluorescence of the single Trp66, monitoring its local environment (Figure 5B). Transition temperatures and van't Hoff enthalpies describing the thermal transitions of the SAK variants are summarized in Table S3.

Analysis of the temperature dependences of ellipticity at 215 nm for the SAK variants clearly shows that, based on the thermal stability of the secondary structures, the proteins in both His-tagged and native forms can be ordered as follows: **STAR > 42D > STAR 3A > 42D 3A**. Analogous comparison of thermal transitions obtained from intrinsic tryptophan

fluorescence indicates a slightly modified order of thermal stabilities for both His-tagged and native SAK variants: **STAR > STAR 3A > 42D > 42D 3A**. The SAK 42D 3A variants (both His-tagged and native) are the least stable, as they aggregate at elevated temperatures. This was detected through visual inspection of the samples in cuvettes during thermal denaturation, as well as by the decreased reversibility of attaining secondary structure upon thermal transition (Figure S3). Aggregation of the native form of SAK 42D 3A is clearly evident (Figure 5A, second row), where a thermal transition occurs at $T_m = 45^\circ\text{C}$, with a relative amplitude of ~ 0.2 , followed by a second transition indicating protein aggregation. The aggregation of SAK 42D 3A is most likely a consequence of the introduced mutations, which (i) increased the overall hydrophobicity of the protein structure by replacing three charged residues with hydrophobic alanines [47,48] and (ii) markedly reduced protein stability, thereby enhancing the likelihood of formation of aggregation-prone conformations [49].

These findings led to the exclusion of data from CD and fluorescence measurements for further analysis, as the thermal transition parameters were likely affected by aggregation in the temperature range of the transition. A similar decrease in reversibility upon thermal transition was observed for both His-tagged and native forms of SAK STAR 3A. Analysis of the thermal transitions revealed the appearance of aggregation in the form of a mist, but only at high temperatures after the end of thermal transitions. Therefore, the obtained parameters of the thermal transition of SAK STAR 3A were used for further analysis. Although re-cooling led to partial or full reversibility of the secondary structure in both forms of SAK, re-heating did not show a thermal transition, indicating that the transitions are irreversible. This suggests that the conformational states of the SAK proteins resemble a molten-globule state.

In the effort to avoid protein concentration effect on the transition temperature of thermal transitions, we analysed the thermal transition obtained by monitoring the temperature dependence of ellipticity and fluorescence of SAK variants at the equal protein concentrations, 10 μM . Based on comparison of such thermal transitions, we conclude: (i) the proteins thermal transitions are non-two state transitions, i.e. in the presence of thermal transition stable intermediate(s) occur, as indicated by different T_m values from CD and fluorescence measurements, (ii) the presence of His-tag does not affect the thermal transitions, as the T_m values of the His-tagged and native forms are nearly identical when measured by the same method, and (iii) the thermal and pH-stabilities of the studied SAK variants do not correlate.

Close examination of the thermal transitions monitored by tryptophan fluorescence reveals that both SAK 42D and SAK STAR are significantly less cooperative, quantitatively indicated by lower ΔH_{vH} values (Table S3). In fact, decoupling of the thermal transition of α -helix containing Trp66 (Figure 1B) from the rest of the proteins structure in the case of SAK 42D and SAK STAR demonstrates also in the differences of values of transition temperature obtained by ellipticity and fluorescence, shown as ΔT_m in Figure 5C.

Figure 5. Thermal transitions of SAK variants measured by (A) CD and (B) fluorescence. (C) Difference, ΔT_m , between T_m obtained from ellipticity and fluorescence for the specific SAK variant. The top row displays the transitions of His-tagged forms, while the bottom row shows those of the native forms. The SAK variants are represented by the following color scheme: 42D (blue), STAR (red), 42D 3A (green), and STAR 3A (black). Solid symbols represent His-tagged forms, while empty symbols indicate native forms.

3.4. *Chromogenic activity assay of SAK variants.* To evaluate the functional activity of individual SAK variants, we performed a chromogenic activity assay that compares His-tagged forms with their corresponding native (tag-cleaved) proteins (Figure 6). This assay measures the ability of each SAK variant to catalyse the conversion of plasminogen to plasmin through formation of a ternary complex (SAK/plasmin/plasminogen). The generated plasmin then hydrolyses a chromogenic substrate, releasing a chromophoric group that can be quantitatively monitored by absorbance at 405 nm. Notably, in three out of the four variants studied, the removal of the His-tag resulted in an increase in activity (Figure 6A-D), consistent with previous reports indicating that affinity tags can interfere with enzymatic function

[28,30,34,35,37,38]. The only exception was SAK 42D 3A, where the difference between the tagged and native forms was negligible.

Kinetic parameter, the accelerator parameters, a_{app} , characterizing the acceleration of the reaction by SAK, are summarized in Table S4. From comparison of the accelerator parameters follows that both native forms of SAK STAR consistently exhibited the highest catalytic activity, while SAK 42D 3A was the least active (Figure 6E).

Figure 6. SAK chromogenic activity assay. The SAK variants are distinguished by specific colours: 42D (blue) (A), STAR (red) (B), 42D 3A (green) (C), and STAR 3A (black) (D). His-tagged forms kinetics are represented by solid lines, and native forms kinetics by dotted lines. SAK reaction kinetics are described by the apparent acceleration constant, a_{app} (s^{-2}), reflecting time-dependent catalytic enhancement of the coupled reaction mechanism. The acceleration is shown by histograms: His-tagged forms of SAK (solid histograms) and native SAK forms (empty).

Our experimental results do not provide a direct explanation for why the SAK STAR variants exhibit higher activity than the SAK 42D variants. Similarly, the influence of the His-tag on the activity of individual variants can only be inferred indirectly by comparing its effects on protein stability. Notably, both activity and stability appear to be negatively affected by the presence of the His-tag. Since reduced stability is often associated with decreased structural

rigidity, it may be hypothesized that the stability and/or rigidity of the α -helical region might contribute in determining SAK activity.

Conclusions

Our systematic analysis of four SAK variants in His-tagged and native forms demonstrated that the presence of the N-terminal His-tag: (i) significantly decreases the protein pH stabilities, as demonstrated by transitions detected by tryptophan fluorescence and the far-UV ellipticity, (ii) slightly decreases the efficiency of SAK-mediated plasminogen-to-plasmin conversion in three of the SAK variants (except SAK 42D 3A), and (iii) has no apparent effect on the thermal stability of the studied SAK variants (Figure 7). Consequently, no apparent correlation was observed between the thermal stability and the destabilizing effect of the His-tag on pH transitions. Our analyses clearly indicate the existence of intermediate state(s) both in the transition induced by temperature and the pH, as evidenced by different T_m values and different pK_a values of the given protein obtained from ellipticity and fluorescence dependences.

Among the tested variants, SAK STAR, due to its highest conformational stability and best functional properties among the tested SAK variants, emerged as a promising candidate for further optimization. In contrast, SAK 42D 3A, which carries three mutations reducing the SAK immunogenicity, was identified as the most unstable variant with significantly decreased colloidal stability.

In conclusion, the findings of this work and the recent report [39] suggest that modifications of either the N- or C-termini may influence biophysical as well as functional properties of SAK. This opens another potential direction of rational design of the properties of this promising thrombolytics not only within the existing sequence but also through expanding the protein termini.

Finally, based on published studies and our own analysis, it should be emphasized that the effects of His-tags on proteins and enzymes are often multifaceted and highly dependent on the specific structural context of the protein. Indeed, recent findings [31] have demonstrated that His-tags can exert negative, positive, or negligible effects on protein stability. Although predictive software tools have recently been developed to estimate the influence of His-tags on protein structure [33], the impact of a His-tag on a particular protein property must, in general, still be validated experimentally.

Figure 7. A schematic overview of the effect of N-terminal His-tag removal on the properties of studied SAK variants.

Acknowledgements

This work has been funded by the EU NextGenerationEU through the Recovery and Resilience Plan for Slovakia under the project 09I01-03-V04-00041. This work has been funded by the EU NextGenerationEU through the Recovery and Resilience Plan for Slovakia under the project No. 09-I02-03-V01-00021. This project was also supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the grant agreements CETOCOEN No. 857560 and No. CLARA 101136607. Supported by the project National Institute for Neurology Research (No. LX22NPO5107) financed by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

References

- [1] GBD 2019 Stroke Collaborators, Global, regional, and national burden of stroke and its risk factors, 1990-2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019, *Lancet Neurol* 20 (2021) 795–820. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(21\)00252-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(21)00252-0).
- [2] N. Eberhardt, M.G. Noval, R. Kaur, L. Amadori, M. Gildea, S. Sajja, D. Das, B. Cilhoroz, O.J. Stewart, D.M. Fernandez, R. Shamailova, A. Vasquez Guillen, S. Jangra, M. Schotsaert, J.D. Newman, P. Faries, T. Maldonado, C. Rockman, A. Rapkiewicz, K.A. Stapleford, N. Narula, K.J. Moore, C. Giannarelli, SARS-CoV-2 infection triggers pro-atherogenic inflammatory responses in human coronary vessels, *Nat Cardiovasc Res* 2 (2023) 899–916. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44161-023-00336-5>.

- [3] W.J. Powers, A.A. Rabinstein, T. Ackerson, O.M. Adeoye, N.C. Bambakidis, K. Becker, J. Biller, M. Brown, B.M. Demaerschalk, B. Hoh, E.C. Jauch, C.S. Kidwell, T.M. Leslie-Mazwi, B. Ovbiagele, P.A. Scott, K.N. Sheth, A.M. Southerland, D.V. Summers, D.L. Tirschwell, American Heart Association Stroke Council, 2018 Guidelines for the Early Management of Patients With Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Guideline for Healthcare Professionals From the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association, *Stroke* 49 (2018) e46–e110. <https://doi.org/10.1161/STR.000000000000158>.
- [4] Y. Dundar, R. Hill, R. Dickson, T. Walley, Comparative efficacy of thrombolytics in acute myocardial infarction: a systematic review, *QJM* 96 (2003) 103–113. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcg016>.
- [5] H.-Y. Li, Y.-B. Wang, X.-Y. Ren, J. Wang, H.-S. Wang, Y.-H. Jin, Comparative Efficacy and Safety of Thrombolytic Agents for Pulmonary Embolism: A Bayesian Network Meta-Analysis, *Pharmacology* 108 (2023) 111–126. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000527668>.
- [6] D. Nikitin, S. Choi, J. Mican, M. Toul, W.-S. Ryu, J. Damborsky, R. Mikulik, D.-E. Kim, Development and Testing of Thrombolytics in Stroke, *J Stroke* 23 (2021) 12–36. <https://doi.org/10.5853/jos.2020.03349>.
- [7] J. Mican, M. Toul, D. Bednar, J. Damborsky, Structural Biology and Protein Engineering of Thrombolytics, *Comput Struct Biotechnol J* 17 (2019) 917–938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2019.06.023>.
- [8] S.E. Miller, S.J. Warach, Evolving Thrombolytics: from Alteplase to Tenecteplase, *Neurotherapeutics* 20 (2023) 664–678. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13311-023-01391-3>.
- [9] A.M. Alasheev, E.V. Lantsova, D.A. Tretyakov, [Efficacy and safety of non-immunogenic staphylokinase in the ischemic stroke in real-world clinical practice in the Sverdlovsk region], *Zh Nevrol Psikhiatr Im S S Korsakova* 123 (2023) 74–79. <https://doi.org/10.17116/jnevro202312307174>.
- [10] E.I. Gusev, M.Y. Martynov, A.A. Nikonov, N.A. Shamalov, M.P. Semenov, E.A. Gerasimets, E.B. Yarovaya, A.M. Semenov, A.I. Archakov, S.S. Markin, FRIDA Study Group, Non-immunogenic recombinant staphylokinase versus alteplase for patients with acute ischaemic stroke 4·5 h after symptom onset in Russia (FRIDA): a randomised, open label, multicentre, parallel-group, non-inferiority trial, *Lancet Neurol* 20 (2021) 721–728. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(21\)00210-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(21)00210-6).
- [11] R. Nedaeinia, H. Faraji, S.H. Javanmard, G.A. Ferns, M. Ghayour-Mobarhan, M. Goli, B. Mashkani, M. Nedaeinia, M.H.H. Haghighi, M. Ranjbar, Bacterial staphylokinase as a promising third-generation drug in the treatment for vascular occlusion, *Mol Biol Rep* 47 (2020) 819–841. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11033-019-05167-x>.
- [12] C.H. Lack, Staphylokinase; an activator of plasma protease, *Nature* 161 (1948) 559. <https://doi.org/10.1038/161559b0>.
- [13] H.R. Lijnen, B. Van Hoef, F. De Cock, K. Okada, S. Ueshima, O. Matsuo, D. Collen, On the mechanism of fibrin-specific plasminogen activation by staphylokinase, *J Biol Chem* 266 (1991) 11826–11832.
- [14] A. Gase, E. Birch-Hirschfeld, K.H. Gührs, M. Hartmann, S. Vetterman, G. Damaschun, H. Damaschun, K. Gast, R. Misselwitz, D. Zirwer, The thermostability of natural variants of bacterial plasminogen-activator staphylokinase, *Eur J Biochem* 223 (1994) 303–308. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1432-1033.1994.tb18995.x>.
- [15] S.M. Vanderschueren, J.M. Stassen, D. Collen, On the immunogenicity of recombinant staphylokinase in patients and in animal models, *Thromb Haemost* 72 (1994) 297–301.
- [16] D. Collen, L. Stockx, H. Lacroix, R. Suy, S. Vanderschueren, Recombinant staphylokinase variants with altered immunoreactivity. IV: Identification of variants with reduced antibody induction but intact potency, *Circulation* 95 (1997) 463–472. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.95.2.463>.

- [17] S. Frokjaer, D.E. Otzen, Protein drug stability: a formulation challenge, *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 4 (2005) 298–306. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd1695>.
- [18] M.-R. Ki, S.P. Pack, Fusion tags to enhance heterologous protein expression, *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 104 (2020) 2411–2425. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-020-10402-8>.
- [19] A.I. Freitas, L. Domingues, T.Q. Aguiar, Tag-mediated single-step purification and immobilization of recombinant proteins toward protein-engineered advanced materials, *J Adv Res* 36 (2022) 249–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2021.06.010>.
- [20] J.-J. Yuan, S.-L. Geng, T.-Y. Wang, Research Progress Fusion Tags for Recombinant Protein Production, *Biotechnol Appl Biochem* (2025) e2749. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bab.2749>.
- [21] M. Carson, D.H. Johnson, H. McDonald, C. Brouillette, L.J. Delucas, His-tag impact on structure, *Acta Crystallogr D Biol Crystallogr* 63 (2007) 295–301. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S09074444906052024>.
- [22] A. Chant, C.M. Kraemer-Pecore, R. Watkin, G.G. Kneale, Attachment of a histidine tag to the minimal zinc finger protein of the *Aspergillus nidulans* gene regulatory protein AreA causes a conformational change at the DNA-binding site, *Protein Expr Purif* 39 (2005) 152–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pep.2004.10.017>.
- [23] Y.-W. Lin, T.-L. Ying, L.-F. Liao, Molecular modeling and dynamics simulation of a histidine-tagged cytochrome *b₅*, *J Mol Model* 17 (2011) 971–978. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00894-010-0795-4>.
- [24] M. Amor-Mahjoub, J.-P. Suppini, N. Gomez-Vrielyunck, M. Ladjimi, The effect of the hexahistidine-tag in the oligomerization of HSC70 constructs, *J Chromatogr B Analyt Technol Biomed Life Sci* 844 (2006) 328–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2006.07.031>.
- [25] I. Fonda, M. Kenig, V. Gaberc-Porekar, P. Pristovaek, V. Menart, Attachment of histidine tags to recombinant tumor necrosis factor-alpha drastically changes its properties, *ScientificWorldJournal* 2 (2002) 1312–1325. <https://doi.org/10.1100/tsw.2002.215>.
- [26] A.-C. Freydank, W. Brandt, B. Dräger, Protein structure modeling indicates hexahistidine-tag interference with enzyme activity, *Proteins* 72 (2008) 173–183. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.21905>.
- [27] A. Goel, D. Colcher, J.S. Koo, B.J. Booth, G. Pavlinkova, S.K. Batra, Relative position of the hexahistidine tag effects binding properties of a tumor-associated single-chain Fv construct, *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1523 (2000) 13–20. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0304-4165\(00\)00086-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0304-4165(00)00086-6).
- [28] K.A. Majorek, M.L. Kuhn, M. Chruszcz, W.F. Anderson, W. Minor, Double trouble-Buffer selection and His-tag presence may be responsible for nonreproducibility of biomedical experiments, *Protein Sci* 23 (2014) 1359–1368. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.2520>.
- [29] Z.C. Zhu, K.K. Gupta, A.R. Slabbekoorn, B.A. Paulson, E.S. Folker, H.V. Goodson, Interactions between EB1 and microtubules: dramatic effect of affinity tags and evidence for cooperative behavior, *J Biol Chem* 284 (2009) 32651–32661. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M109.013466>.
- [30] C. Emoto, N. Murayama, S. Wakiya, H. Yamazaki, Effects of histidine-tag on recombinant human cytochrome P450 3A5 catalytic activity in reconstitution systems, *Drug Metab Lett* 3 (2009) 207–211. <https://doi.org/10.2174/187231209790218109>.
- [31] W.T. Booth, C.R. Schlachter, S. Pote, N. Ussin, N.J. Mank, V. Klapper, L.R. Offermann, C. Tang, B.K. Hurlburt, M. Chruszcz, Impact of an N-terminal Polyhistidine Tag on Protein Thermal Stability, *ACS Omega* 3 (2018) 760–768. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.7b01598>.

- [32] M.C. Thielges, J.K. Chung, J.Y. Axup, M.D. Fayer, Influence of histidine tag attachment on picosecond protein dynamics, *Biochemistry* 50 (2011) 5799–5805. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bi2003923>.
- [33] R. Gerulskis, S.D. Minter, Terminator: A Software Package for Fast and Local Optimization of His-Tag Placement for Protein Affinity Purification, *ACS Bio Med Chem Au* 5 (2025) 55–65. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbiochemau.4c00055>.
- [34] Y. Aslantas, N.B. Surmeli, Effects of N-Terminal and C-Terminal Polyhistidine Tag on the Stability and Function of the Thermophilic P450 CYP119, *Bioinorg Chem Appl* 2019 (2019) 8080697. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/8080697>.
- [35] F. Elgharbi, H. Ben Hlima, S. Ben Mabrouk, A. Hmida-Sayari, Expression of a Copper Activated Xylanase in Yeast: Location of the His-Tag in the Protein Significantly Affects the Enzymatic Properties, *Mol Biotechnol* 65 (2023) 1109–1118. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12033-022-00606-w>.
- [36] M.Z. Mišković, M. Wojtyś, M. Winiewska-Szajewska, B. Wielgus-Kutrowska, M. Matković, D. Domazet Jurašin, Z. Štefanić, A. Bzowska, I. Leščić Ašler, Location Is Everything: Influence of His-Tag Fusion Site on Properties of Adenylosuccinate Synthetase from *Helicobacter pylori*, *Int J Mol Sci* 25 (2024) 7613. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms25147613>.
- [37] J.-M. Park, J.-H. Kim, K.-S. Choi, H.-J. Kwon, Deleterious Effects of Histidine Tagging to the SH3b Cell Wall-Binding Domain on Recombinant Endolysin Activity, *J Microbiol Biotechnol* 34 (2024) 2331–2337. <https://doi.org/10.4014/jmb.2408.08003>.
- [38] J.M. de Almeida, V.R. Moure, M. Müller-Santos, E.M. de Souza, F.O. Pedrosa, D.A. Mitchell, N. Krieger, Tailoring recombinant lipases: keeping the His-tag favors esterification reactions, removing it favors hydrolysis reactions, *Sci Rep* 8 (2018) 10000. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-27579-8>.
- [39] P. Kaur, D. Sethi, M.D. Hade, J. Kaur, K.L. Dikshit, C-terminal lysine residues enhance plasminogen activation by inducing conformational flexibility and stabilization of activator complex of staphylokinase with plasmin, *Arch Biochem Biophys* 743 (2023) 109671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.abb.2023.109671>.
- [40] M. Petrenčáková, R. Varhač, T. Kožár, M. Nemergut, D. Jancura, M.-S. Schwer, E. Sedlák, Conformational properties of LOV2 domain and its C450A variant within broad pH region, *Biophys Chem* 259 (2020) 106337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpc.2020.106337>.
- [41] E. Dušeková, K. Garajová, R. Yavaşer, R. Varhač, E. Sedlák, Hofmeister effect on catalytic properties of chymotrypsin is substrate-dependent, *Biophys Chem* 243 (2018) 8–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpc.2018.10.002>.
- [42] G. Žoldák, D. Jancura, E. Sedlák, The fluorescence intensities ratio is not a reliable parameter for evaluation of protein unfolding transitions, *Protein Sci* 26 (2017) 1236–1239. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.3170>.
- [43] N. Mandi, S. Soorapaneni, S. Rewanwar, P. Kotwal, B. Prasad, G. Mandal, S. Padmanabhan, High yielding recombinant Staphylokinase in bacterial expression system-cloning, expression, purification and activity studies, *Protein Expr Purif* 64 (2009) 69–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pep.2008.10.010>.
- [44] M. Toul, D. Nikitin, M. Marek, J. Damborsky, Z. Prokop, Extended Mechanism and Rate-Limiting Step of the Plasminogen Activator Staphylokinase Revealed by Global Kinetic Analysis, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2021-x5qdj>.
- [45] S. Lewis, T. Hempel, J. Jiménez-Luna, M. Gastegger, Y. Xie, A.Y.K. Foong, V.G. Satorras, O. Abdin, B.S. Veeling, I. Zaporozhets, Y. Chen, S. Yang, A.E. Foster, A. Schneuing, J. Nigam, F. Barbero, V. Stimper, A. Campbell, J. Yim, M. Lienen, Y. Shi, S. Zheng, H. Schulz, U. Munir, R. Sordillo, R. Tomioka, C. Clementi, F. Noé, Scalable emulation of

- protein equilibrium ensembles with generative deep learning, *Science* 389 (2025) eadv9817. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adv9817>.
- [46] Y. Goto, M. Adachi, H. Muta, M. So, Salt-induced formations of partially folded intermediates and amyloid fibrils suggests a common underlying mechanism, *Biophys Rev* 10 (2018) 493–502. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12551-017-0370-7>.
- [47] K.L. Shaw, G.R. Grimsley, G.I. Yakovlev, A.A. Makarov, C.N. Pace, The effect of net charge on the solubility, activity, and stability of ribonuclease Sa, *Protein Sci* 10 (2001) 1206–1215. <https://doi.org/10.1110/ps.440101>.
- [48] S.R. Trevino, J.M. Scholtz, C.N. Pace, Amino acid contribution to protein solubility: Asp, Glu, and Ser contribute more favorably than the other hydrophilic amino acids in RNase Sa, *J Mol Biol* 366 (2007) 449–460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2006.10.026>.
- [49] S. Seshadri, K.A. Oberg, V.N. Uversky, Mechanisms and consequences of protein aggregation: the role of folding intermediates, *Curr Protein Pept Sci* 10 (2009) 456–463. <https://doi.org/10.2174/138920309789351976>.